

Influencing Factors and Global Variations of Teachers' ICT Skills Value Identity

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Abstract

With the rapid development of information and communication technology (ICT) and its increasing integration into educational practices, the importance of teachers' ICT skills has gained global attention. Many countries now require teachers to incorporate ICT into their teaching activities to enhance educational quality and promote equity. However, despite the recognition of the importance of ICT skills, teachers often struggle to effectively utilize the technologies into their teaching. Previous research has overlooked the role of teachers' value identity on ICT skills, which is crucial for their motivation and effective application. The study uses data from the 2018 Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS 2018), selecting 50,689 primary school teachers across various countries as the sample. Meanwhile, the Value-Based Adoption Model (VAM) is adopted to analyze the influencing factors. Results show significant variations in teachers' ICT skills value identity across countries, with positive school climate, high job satisfaction, and students' ICT use positively influencing the ICT skills value identity. However, initial preparation and self-efficacy in traditional teaching negatively impact value identity, while barriers surprisingly have a positive effect. This study proposes a facilitation and hindrance model of teachers' ICT skills value identity, highlighting the need for practical ICT experiences in teacher education programs. The findings provide valuable insights for educational practitioners aiming to enhance teachers' ICT integration in the global scope.

Keywords: *ICT skills, value identity, influencing factors, TALIS 2018.*

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Introduction

With the development of information and communication technology (ICT) and its application in education, new requirements have been placed on teacher training. In many countries or regions, teachers are required to integrate ICT into their teaching activities (Wikan & Molster, 2011; Wang & Zhao, 2021; Bai et al., 2021). However, most teachers were unable to integrate ICT to achieve specific learning goals smoothly (Heitink et al., 2016). Previous studies indicated that this problem can be caused by inadequate preparation during teacher preparation programs or inadequate

knowledge of integrating technology into their teaching (Tondeur et al., 2018). Among them, the research on teachers' value identity on ICT skills has been seriously ignored. As an essential element in teaching and learning, ICT should be mastered by teachers based on a good value identity. Due to the lack of value identity of ICT skills, it is difficult for teachers to have sufficient motivation to learn and master ICT-related knowledge and apply it effectively in practical teaching. Since value identity is critical, the question arises as to how the value identity of teachers around ICT skills can be improved at all. This study divides this question into the following two research questions (RQ): What is the value identity of teachers in relation to ICT skills worldwide? What are the influencing factors of teachers' value identity on ICT skills?

Teachers' ICT Skills

ICT refers to a set of activities that promote the collection, storage, processing, dissemination and presentation of information by electronic means (Cvetković et al., 2019). Since the beginning of the new century, ICT has become the focus of global attention. Many countries and international organizations have tried to improve the quality of education and promote educational equity (Lim et al., 2020). Teachers are the main body for carrying out educational and teaching activities. The use of ICT to promote education and teaching cannot be separated from teachers' mastery of ICT skills. Teacher ICT skills are the ability of teachers to use ICT effectively to teach and promote student learning (Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2015). ICT can provide teachers with a variety of sources of information and means of acquisition in educational practice, innovate teaching models, turn traditional classroom teaching on its head, and create conditions for teachers' professional development and lifelong learning (Albion et al., 2015).

The significant role of teachers' ICT skills in promoting education and teaching has been recognized by previous researchers. Wikan & Molster (2011) believed that efforts to integrate ICT into most aspects of school practice have received considerable attention in the educational systems of many countries over the last decade and that ICT in schools will improve subject learning. Schibeci et al. (2008) argued that teachers have a central role in developing new models of learning which is critical when integrating ICT into classrooms. In addition, ICT can offer benefits for teachers such as supporting personalized pathways; monitoring progress; providing for anytime and anywhere learning; enabling independent and collaborative learning; and developing new models of teaching and learning (Hammond et al., 2011; Brun & Hinostroza, 2014; Tondeur et al., 2018; Rubach & Lazarides, 2021).

Influencing Factors of Teachers' Value Identity on ICT Skill

To improve teachers' ICT skills, understanding and improving teachers' value identity on ICT skills is an essential factor. Value identity refers to the internal recognition or consensus of social members or organizations on a certain type of value in social activities (Van der Werff et al., 2013). Through this recognition or consensus, they form their value orientation in social practice to determine and pursue their ideals and beliefs. It is the attitude and even observation of social members towards social value norms. Teacher value identity regarding ICT skills is the prerequisite for the effective technology utilization (Ertmer et al., 2012). Even teachers do not have a strong emphasis on ICT skills, they may use ICT for certain reasons, such as the requirements of school leaders, parental expectations or social pressure. However, the application of ICT in the case of low-value identity is difficult to promote teachers' long-term and sustainable application of ICT, especially teachers' active exploration and innovation. Therefore, the use of ICT based on teachers' value identity is the correct future development path in line with long-term interests.

Studies used different methods to examine the factors influencing teachers' use of ICT in different countries or regions. Uluyol & Sahin (2016) stated that learning resources, support and opportunities are key factors in increasing teachers' motivation to improve the level and quality of

ICT use in the classroom using semi-structured interviews to assess ICT primary school teachers to examine usage and its motivators. Ibieta et al. (2017) found that teachers' perception of the impact of ICT on professional practice is the main factor related to their use of ICT inside and outside the classroom, using a survey to assess their activities and perceptions related to it to characterize ICT. Chen et al. (2019) studied primary and secondary school teachers and proposed a model of ICT use in teaching and learning, which indicated that the willingness to use, frequency of use, ICT-based teaching competence, degree of helpfulness, and context of use are the five main factors.

Although previous studies made a great contribution to the analysis of the factors affecting teachers' ICT use, as highlighted in this study, research on the factors affecting teachers' ICT use should focus on their identity of value based ICT skills. However, there are limited studies analyzing the factors influencing teachers' value identity related to ICT skills. This study plans to put focus on the dimension of value identity, examines the current situation of teachers' value identity related to ICT skills around the world, and reveals the influencing factors on teachers' value identity.

Theoretical Perspective and Research Hypothesis

The Value-Based Adoption Model (VAM) developed by Kim et al. (2007) was based on the perceived value theory of Zeithaml (1988) and Davis' (1989) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). VAM analyzes the factors affecting users' acceptance of mobile Internet from the perspective of maximizing users' perceived value. In the VAM, two key factors that influence users' value recognition of technology: benefit, and sacrifice. The perception of technical product benefit is affected by usefulness and enjoyment, and then affects value identity, while the perception of technical product sacrifice can be affected by technicality and perceived fee, and then affects value identification. However, the theoretical model only points out the factors related to the technology itself, whereas fails to include the social influencing factors and corresponding psychological influencing factors of technology users in certain social situations.

Based on the basic idea of VAM, combined with the relevant influencing factors mentioned in the above literature review, this study constructs the influencing factor model of ICT competency value identity in the educational situation, as shown in Figure 1. The factors influencing teachers' value identity in relation to ICT skills can also be divided into benefits and sacrifices. Benefit factors include initial preparation, school climate, job satisfaction, students' ICT use, and teachers' ICT activities. In the context of this study, initial preparation refers to preparing teachers for ICT skills in pre-service training. In this study, it is tentatively assumed that the higher the level of preparation in ICT skills, the more the teacher will feel the benefits of ICT skills and the more the teacher agrees with the value of ICT. School climate is a multifaceted concept that includes safety, relationships, engagement in teaching and learning, institutional environment, and school improvement activities (Thapa et al., 2013). Job satisfaction refers to the sense of fulfillment and satisfaction that teachers experience from their work as teachers (Locke, 1969). This study also assumes that positive school climate and high job satisfaction contribute to teachers feeling the benefits of using ICT and enhancing the identity value of ICT skills. Students' ICT use refers to the use of ICT in their daily learning activities. Teachers' ICT activities refer to their use of ICT in daily teaching or professional development activities. This study considers that the use of ICT by both teachers themselves and the students they target in daily teaching and learning activities can improve teachers' perceptions of the usefulness of ICT skills and thereby strengthen value identity.

Figure 1. Hypotheses of Influencing Factors of Teachers' ICT Skills Value Identity

Sacrifice factors include barriers and self-efficiency. Barriers are types of obstacles that prevent teachers from teaching in schools and promoting their professional development. When teachers face many obstacles in school, they must devote their energy to overcome the obstacles using ICT and reduce value identity. Bandura et al. (1997) defined self-efficacy beliefs as individuals' perceptions of their ability to plan and implement a particular behavior. In the areas of teacher training and educational effectiveness, increasing emphasis has been placing on the importance of teacher self-efficacy (Kasalak & Dagyar, 2020; Klassen & Tze, 2014). In contrast to previous studies on the influence of teachers' self-efficacy of ICT skills on their application, this study analyzes the influence of teachers' self-efficacy in teaching on the value identity of ICT skills. This study hypothesizes that teachers who have a higher sense of self-efficacy regarding original teaching will think that they do not need to be proficient in ICT skills to reduce value identity.

According to the above description of the relationship between variables in the influencing factor model of teachers' value identity on ICT skills, this study generally puts forward the following research hypotheses:

- Hypothesis 1:** The initial preparation will directly promote teachers' value identity on ICT skills.
- Hypothesis 2:** A positive school climate will directly promote teachers' value identity on ICT skills.
- Hypothesis 3:** High job satisfaction will directly promote teachers' value identity on ICT skills.
- Hypothesis 4:** Students' ICT use will directly promote teachers' value identity on ICT skills.
- Hypothesis 5:** Teachers' ICT activities will directly promote their value identity on ICT skills.
- Hypothesis 6:** Barriers will directly hinder teachers' value identity on ICT skills.
- Hypothesis 7:** Teachers' self-efficacy will directly promote their value identity on ICT skills.

Materials and Methods

Data Source

This study employed the Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS 2018) as the main data source. TALIS is an ongoing large-scale survey of teachers, school leaders, and their learning environments conducted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). In addition to different countries, the survey also includes different levels of education. We selected 50,689 teachers in primary education across different countries as the sample. A 58-item questionnaire were used to measure teachers' background and qualifications, current work, professional development, feedback, teaching, school climate and job satisfaction, and teacher mobility.

Data Collection and Analysis

Means treatment or recoding of special independent variables. When measuring independent variables, some independent variables were completed not by a single item but by a group of items. Thus, the independent variables of school climate, job satisfaction, barriers and self-efficacy had to be averaged separately. In addition, the independent variable of teachers' ICT activities was determined by the item of the three dichotomous options and therefore needs to be recorded.

The standardization treatment of the dependent variables. The dependent variables consisted of two elements: teachers' demand and attention to ICT skills. In addition, the selection of options was varied as well. The former was four points and the latter was three points. Therefore, it is necessary to standardize the dependent variables. Since the least common multiple of the two is 12, the maximum value of the option range of both was changed to 12. When the two were added together, the range of values of the dependent variable was 7-24.

Linear regression analysis. After the above treatment, all the variables are interval scaled. Therefore, when analyzing the effect of the respective variables on the dependent variable, linear regression analysis can be used to test the effect of the influencing factors in the research hypothesis.

Results

Teachers' Value Identity on ICT Skills around the World

As shown in Table 1, this section counts the descriptive levels of teachers' recognition of the value of ICT skills in different countries or regions. Although more than 40 countries or regions participated in the 2018 TALIS survey, based on the real data, this study counted 14 countries or regions where primary school teachers participated in the survey, with the number of participants ranging from 1,422 to 8,843. Other countries or regions participated in teacher surveys or headmaster surveys at other educational levels. Of the primary school teachers in these 14 countries or regions, 2,592 did not respond to the identification question on the value of ICT skills, resulting in a final valid sample of 48,097.

Among them, the country with the highest ICT skills value identity of teachers is Viet Nam, with an average level of 19.93. Other countries or regions with the average level of value identity of teachers above 18 include Spain, Argentina, and Japan. The country with the lowest average level of the value identity is Denmark at 14.57, while the average levels in England and Turkey are lower than 16 as well. Geographically, the countries or regions listed above range from the Western world to the Eastern world, and from developed countries to developing countries, in terms of stage of development. However, no matter which type of country or region is divided, it is difficult to find the reasons for the differences in the ICT skills value identity of teachers across different countries or regions.

Table 1. Value Identity on ICT Skills of Teachers in Various Countries or Regions

Country or region	N	Mean	SD	SE	Min.	Max.
Australia	2695	17.52	3.850	.074	7	24
Belgium	2534	17.04	4.127	.081	7	24
Argentina	2262	18.12	3.960	.083	7	24
Denmark	2377	14.57	4.197	.086	7	24
England	1841	15.60	3.913	.091	7	24
Japan	3232	18.07	3.563	.062	7	24
Korea	3093	16.04	4.128	.074	7	24
Netherlands	1422	17.02	4.064	.107	7	24
Spain	7123	18.32	3.544	.042	7	24
Sweden	2126	16.58	4.107	.089	7	24
Chinese Taipei	3456	17.11	4.003	.068	7	24
Turkey	3120	15.68	3.912	.070	7	24
United Arab Emirates	8843	16.62	3.900	.041	7	24
Viet Nam	3973	19.93	3.349	.053	7	24
Total	48097	17.19	4.060	.018	7	24

Influencing Factors of Teachers' Value Identity on ICT Skills

The regression model was tested for multicollinearity via the examination of the covariance statistics, the variance inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance. As a rule of thumb, if the VIF of a variable exceeds 10, it means that the variable is highly covariate and can cause problems in the regression analysis. The tolerance values of these variables ranged from 0.80 to 0.91, and the VIF values ranged from 1.09 to 1.25, indicating that multicollinearity does not pose a threat to the parameter estimation in this study.

The regression analysis in Table 2 shows the effect of potential influences on value identity. Among the benefit variables, SC ($\beta = .524, p < .05$), JS ($\beta = .893, p < .05$), SU ($\beta = .064, p < .05$), and TA ($\beta = .0195, p < .05$) significantly and positively affect teachers' ICT skills value identity, which supports research hypotheses 2, 3, 4, 5, respectively. But IP ($\beta = -.643, p < .05$) significantly and negatively affects teachers' ICT skills value identity, which is contrary to research hypothesis 1, indicating that initial preparation does not promote the value identity, but rather causes a hindering effect. Among the sacrifice variables, SE ($\beta = -.107, p < .05$) had a significant negative effect on the value identity, which supports hypothesis 7. However, BA ($\beta = .583, p < .05$) had a significant positive effect on the value identity, which is contrary to research hypothesis 6. This suggests that rather than hindering teachers' value identity, barriers promote the indicator. In general, the core idea of VAM can only be used to a certain extent to explain the factors influencing teachers' value identity on ICT skills. These results need to be further explored.

Table 2. The Impact of Potential Influencing Factors on Value Identity

Variables	β	SE	t	Sig.
Benefit variables				
IP	-.643	.024	-27.207	.000
SC	.524	.047	11.167	.000
JS	.893	.091	9.861	.000
SU	.064	.026	2.493	.013
TA	.0195	.023	8.479	.000
Sacrifice variables				
BA	.583	.041	14.363	.000
SE	-.107	.049	-2.158	.031

Discussion

In the descriptive statistics of the teachers' value identity on ICT skills around the world, the level varies from country to country. And it is difficult to find the developmental or geographical reasons. Vietnam is a developing country in Asia with the highest score among countries or regions. Denmark is a developed European country whereas scored the lowest among the countries or regions. Looking at the data alone, it is easy to conclude that teachers' recognition of the value of ICT skills decreases with economic development. However, for Turkey, the value identity on ICT skills of teachers in this developing country is not high. And for Spain, a developed country, the same item has a relatively high value. Geographical analyses are similar to development analysis. There are countries or regions in the East and the West with both high and relatively low scores, such as Japan and South Korea, two Eastern countries, the former of which has a relatively higher value identity compared to the latter. Similarly, Spain and England, two Western countries. The former has a relatively high value identity, while the latter is relatively low. Therefore, neither an analysis based on the level of development nor on geographical distribution is a reliable reason to judge teachers' ICT skills value identity in a country or region. It might be affected by the policies, cultures, and educational systems of different countries or regions. It should also be noted that this study only calculates the scores of the value identity and did not focus on the ranking, which is considered to be of no real significance in the context of value identity research. The real significance lies in how the ICT skills value identity of teachers can be used to improve their ICT integration, so as to promote the high quality of development of teacher education in the global scope.

When analyzing the factors influencing, VAM can explain how the influencing factors affect teachers' ICT skills value identity, but there are some exceptions. Positive school climate, high job satisfaction, the use of ICT skills by both students and teachers can contribute to teachers' perception of technical skills and thus increase their value identity. This reveals that in order to increase the value identity, it is important to pay attention not only to teacher training or training activities related to the technology, but also to the external conditions as well. Researchers and educators agree that school climate has a significant impact on teaching and learning and teachers' ICT skills.

Research shows a positive relationship between the teacher job satisfaction and teacher performance (Renzulli et al., 2010). Job satisfaction also plays a key role in teachers' attitudes, forces, and confidence in their daily work (Caprara et al., 2003; Klassen et al., 2009). Value identity belongs to the category of teachers' attitudes. The results of this study also verify that teachers' job satisfaction can exert a significant impact on ICT skill value identity. In addition, this study confirms that students' and teachers' use of ICT in their daily teaching and learning activities also contributes to teachers' value identity on ICT skills. However, the variable of initial preparation was not consistent with the expectations of this study. Teachers' preparation for ICT skills in pre-service education may have a negative impact on value identity. The possible reason is that most of the knowledge about ICT obtained by teachers in pre-service education is theoretical, and when they go to the workplace, they may find it difficult to teach ICT in practice for the desirable purposes described in the relevant theories. This also reveals that it is not only necessary to teach pre-service teachers theoretical knowledge, but also to give teachers practical ICT teaching experience in pre-service education, so that the teachers could have appropriate expectations of the mastery of ICT skills and lessons. Above all, the discussion should explain how your research has moved the body of scientific knowledge forward.

Figure 2. Hypotheses of Influencing Factors of Teachers' ICT Skills Value Identity

As anticipated, teachers' self-efficacy in the classroom can have a negative impact on the value identity of ICT skills in the sacrifice variable analysis. Because teachers with high self-efficacy in teaching already believe that they are capable to teach effectively and do not see the need for good ICT skills, or even believe that ICT serves as an obstacle to the original teaching, they have a low value identity with it. This also demonstrates the need to put focus on the issues of the value identified to ICT skills by teachers with high teaching self-efficacy. However, the analysis of barriers exceeded the expectations of this study as well. When teachers face various barriers in schools, their recognition of the value of ICT skills does not decrease but rather increases. One possible reason for this is that traditional school teaching is difficult to meet the needs of time and infrastructure, but gives just the right amount of space for ICT to flourish. Teachers are able to truly realize the value of acquiring ICT skills and increase their value identity.

In addition to the VAM's explanation of the influences on teachers' value identity on ICT skills, this study categorizes the potential influences that have been identified, as shown in Figure 2. This study does not devalue the theoretical value of the VAM, which is also effective in explaining teachers' value identity on ICT skills. However, to provide a more concise and intuitive model of influencing factors, this study divides the influencing factors into the facilitating and hindering factors. For instance, positive school climate, high job satisfaction, students' ICT use, teachers' ICT activities, and barriers are the five facilitating factors. These five areas must be addressed to improve teachers' value identity on ICT skills and their ICT integration skills. The barriers themselves are not conducive to both school and teacher development. Rather than trying to deliberately create or add barriers to improving teachers' value identity on ICT skills, this study replaces barriers with barrier experiences in an attempt to show that teachers can instead help improve their value identity by experiencing technology-deficient teaching environments.

Two factors, initial preparation for ICT skills in pre-service teacher education and self-efficacy for traditional teaching, should be favourable for the implementation of teaching, but this study found that they can hinder teachers' value identification with ICT skills. Therefore, how to enable teachers to value ICT skills properly through teacher education programs or courses is a research direction for future practitioners.

Conclusion

In this study, by measuring the value identity degree of ICT skills of primary school teachers in TALIS 2018 and counting them separately by country or region, it can be found that the value identity degree of ICT skill of teachers in different countries or regions was uneven. After that, we referred to the VAM and calculated the levels of potential influences such as initial preparation, school climate, job satisfaction, students' ICT use, teachers' ICT activities, barriers, and self-efficacy for each teacher separately. The linear regression method was used to reveal the relationship between potential influencing factors and value identity. It was found that school climate, job satisfaction, students ICT use, teachers ICT activities, and barriers would positively contribute to value identity, while initial preparation and self-efficiency would hinder value identity. This study puts forward a facilitation and hindrance model of teachers' ICT skills value identity. However, there are limitations to this study, including the fact that it only used TALIS 2018 primary school teachers as a sample and did not include teachers at other levels of education, and this study did not analyze whether there are differences in the influencing factors of teachers' value identity on ICT skills across countries or regions. Future directions could attempt to explore the following questions: Are there any differences in the value identity of ICT skills among teachers at different levels of education? Is the model of teachers' ICT skills value identity proposed in this study applicable to different groups of teachers at different levels? We hope to serve as a catalyst for more researchers to investigate the education and application of teachers' ICT skills.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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